

Evaluation of the Financial Performance of the Boalemo Regency Regional Government: Analysis of Financial Ratios and Their Implications

Hauzan Daffansyah Maloppo, Juriko Abdussamad, Fenti Prihatini Dance Tui

Postgraduate Public Administration, State University of Gorontalo

Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Nov 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Dec 2024; **Published:** 28 Jan 2025

Abstract: This study evaluates the financial performance of the Boalemo Regency Government based on various financial ratio indicators, such as the ratio of independence, effectiveness, efficiency, harmony, and growth. Using the quantitative descriptive analysis method, this study found that Boalemo Regency has a high dependence on transfer income compared to Regional Original Income (PAD), which reflects the low level of regional financial independence. In addition, the efficiency of financial management is a major challenge. The results of this study provide recommendations for local governments to increase financial independence and optimize the use of available resources.

Keywords: Financial Performance, ratio, Implication.

Introduction

Effective and efficient regional financial management is an important pillar in supporting the implementation of regional autonomy in Indonesia, as mandated by Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government and Government Regulation Number 12 of 2019 concerning Regional Financial Management. Regional governments are expected to be able to manage budgets professionally, transparently, and accountably to support regional development and improve public services. Boalemo Regency, as one of the autonomous regions, faces significant challenges related to high dependence on transfer income and low PAD contributions. Therefore, this study focuses on evaluating the financial performance of Boalemo Regency to identify weaknesses and provide strategic recommendations. In the context of regional financial performance, performance evaluation is important to ensure effective, efficient, accountable, and transparent management of public funds. Evaluation of the financial performance of local governments is an important process in assessing the extent to which local governments can manage their finances effectively, efficiently, accountably, and transparently. The Boalemo Regency Government, like other regions, is required to prepare and implement a budget by complying with the principles stipulated in laws and regulations. This evaluation includes analysis of various financial aspects, including budget realization, financial ratios, and level of compliance with regulations. The purpose of this evaluation is to identify strengths and weaknesses in regional financial management and provide recommendations for improvements to improve financial performance.

Regional financial management often prioritizes the interests of certain groups and

becomes ineffective, inefficient, accountable, and transparent. By paying attention to the importance of effective and efficient regional financial management, local governments can ensure quality services to the community, build public trust, and create an environment conducive to sustainable economic growth and prosperity. Thus, these issues show how important effective and efficient regional financial performance is in maintaining financial stability, providing quality public services, and creating an environment conducive to community growth and prosperity.

One method to assess the financial performance of the Regional Government in budget management is through financial ratio analysis against the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBD). Halim (2007: 232) explains that the ratios that can be used to measure the level of accountability of the regional government include the independence ratio, the effectiveness ratio of local revenue (PAD), the efficiency ratio of PAD, the harmony ratio, and the growth ratio.

The independence ratio measures a region's ability to finance government activities, development, and public services by relying on its own sources of income. This ratio shows that the higher the value, the lower the region's dependence on funds from external parties, such as the central or provincial government. Conversely, the lower the independence ratio, the higher the region's dependence on external assistance.

The effectiveness ratio represents the ability of the local government to realize the Regional Original Income (PAD) according to the target that has been set based on the real potential owned by the region. Meanwhile, the efficiency ratio, as explained in Article 3 of Government Regulation Number 12 of 2019, shows how optimal the use of input or costs is to achieve a certain output. The performance of the local government is considered more efficient if the costs incurred are smaller to obtain regional income, and vice versa.

The harmony ratio describes how proportional the budget allocation is between routine spending and development spending. If the allocation for routine spending is larger, then the budget for development spending—which aims to provide infrastructure and economic facilities—will be smaller. Finally, the growth ratio serves to measure the ability of local governments to maintain and improve their financial performance over time. This ratio helps the government analyze previous performance results and plan future improvements.

Therefore, Financial Performance Evaluation of Regional Government is very important. Through financial ratio analysis, the Regional Government can assess the extent of the level of financial independence it has in funding the implementation of its various tasks and functions independently. This ratio functions to determine the region's ability to manage income sourced from Regional Original Income (PAD) as an indicator of the region's success in reducing dependence on funds from the central and provincial governments. In addition, financial ratio analysis can also be used to measure the effectiveness and efficiency in realizing this income according to existing potential, where effectiveness is seen from the region's ability to achieve revenue targets, while efficiency assesses how to use financial resources as minimally as possible to obtain maximum results.

In addition, the regional financial growth ratio is also evaluated to see the dynamics of income and expenditure over time. Through this ratio, it can be measured to what extent the regional government is able to maintain and improve its financial performance from the previous period. Evaluation of financial performance that includes aspects of independence, effectiveness, efficiency, harmony, and growth is very important for every autonomous region in Indonesia in order to identify strengths and weaknesses in its financial management, and formulate more appropriate policies to improve performance in the future.

The financial performance of the Boalemo Regency in organizing regional government

certainly needs to be carried out in order to determine the level of success of the regional government in managing its household. As an autonomous region, Boalemo Regency has a direction and goal for regional finances, namely the creation of regional financial independence. The structure of the Boalemo Regency APBD in 2021 is in accordance with Boalemo Regency Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2020, the structure of the Boalemo Regency APBD in 2022 is in accordance with Boalemo Regency Regional Regulation Number 6 of 2021, and the structure of the Boalemo Regency APBD in 2023 is in accordance with Boalemo Regency Regional Regulation Number 38 of 2022 can be seen in the following table:

TABLE 1.1 Summary of 2021, 2022 and 2023 Regional Budgets

DESCRIPTION	AMOUNT		
	2021	2022	2023
Regional Income	Rp.825,056,087,490.04	Rp.796,509,768,000	Rp.778,131,565,000
Locally-generated revenue	Rp.54,057,606,538.04	Rp.65,000,000,000	Rp.66,625,000,000
Transfer Income	Rp.746,678,180,952	Rp.731,509,768,000	Rp.711,506,565,000
Regional Shopping	Rp.860,891,001,331.65	Rp.669,833,595,504	Rp.778,231,565,000
Operational Shopping	Rp.713,276,079,657.65	Rp.533,851,188,048	Rp.543,003,541,224
Capital Expenditure	Rp.147,614,921,674.00	Rp.135,982,407,456	Rp.117,780,005,576

Source: Data Processed by the Author

Based on the explanation in table 1.1 above, it can be explained that the original regional income in 2021 was worth Rp.54,057,606,538.04 and transfer income worth Rp.746,678,180,952, in 2022 the original regional income is worth Rp.65,000,000,000 and transfer income is worth Rp.746,678,180,952, while in 2023 the original regional registration is worth Rp.66,625,000,000 and transfer registration is worth Rp.711,506,565,000. Transfer income is higher than local revenue every year, so in this condition the Boalemo Regency Government tends to be more dependent on transfer income, both transfer income from the central government and transfer income from other regional governments. This certainly raises questions about the independence and ability of the Boalemo Regency Government to manage regional finances considering that the income obtained will be used to finance regional spending.

Research methods

This study uses a quantitative descriptive approach with data sourced from the 2021–2023 Boalemo Regency Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBD) document. The analysis was conducted using five main financial ratios, namely:

1. **Independence Ratio:** Measuring the extent to which a region is able to finance its activities from PAD.
2. **Effectiveness Ratio:** Assessing the region's ability to realize PAD targets.
3. **Efficiency Ratio:** Evaluate the level of efficiency in using the budget to obtain PAD.
4. **Compatibility Ratio:** Measuring the balance between routine spending and development spending.
5. **Growth Ratio:** Identify revenue and spending growth trends from year to year.

Results and Discussion

1. **Independence Ratio:** Boalemo Regency shows a low independence ratio, with the proportion of PAD to total regional income only reaching 6.55% in 2021, increasing slightly to 8.56% in 2023. This reflects a high dependence on transfer funds from the central government.

2. **Effectiveness Ratio:** The effectiveness of Boalemo Regency's PAD shows an increase, from 95% in 2021 to 102% in 2023. However, this achievement is not significant enough to reduce dependence on transfer income.

3. **Efficiency Ratio:** Efficiency in financial management fluctuates. In 2021, the efficiency ratio was recorded at 85%, but decreased to 78% in 2023, indicating an increase in costs for each unit of revenue earned.

4. **Compatibility Ratio:** The Boalemo Regency spending allocation is still dominated by routine spending, which reaches 70% of the total budget in 2023. This reduces the allocation for productive development spending.

5. **Growth Ratio:** PAD growth shows a positive trend with an average increase of 4% per year. However, routine spending growth is higher than development spending, which can hamper infrastructure development and public services.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study concludes that the financial performance of Boalemo Regency still needs to be improved, especially in terms of financial independence and efficiency. The local government is advised to:

1. **Increasing PAD:** Through diversification of income sources and optimization of local economic potential.
2. **Controlling Routine Spending:** With operational efficiency to increase development budget allocation.
3. **Increasing Transparency:** By utilizing information technology for more accountable financial management.
4. **Building Human Resources Capacity:** With training and technical assistance for regional officials.

With these strategic steps, Boalemo Regency is expected to be able to improve regional financial performance sustainably, support inclusive development, and improve community welfare.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Abdulah, et al. 2022. Stages of Public Policy Making as a Basis for Policy Making. *Muara Peindidikan Journal*, 7(1), 148-155.
2. Abdullah, HM 2014. *Management and Evaluation of Employee Performance*. Yogyakarta; Aswaja Preissindo.
3. Abdussamad, Yuriko. 2013. *Development of Human Resources of State Apparatus Through Competence*. State University of Gorontalo.
4. Ahmad, J. 2012. The Journey of the Old Public Administration (OPA), New Public Management (NPM), New Public Administration (NPS) Towards World Class Public Management. *PRAJA: Peimeirnlahan Scientific Journal*, 1, 1-25.<http://jurnal.umsrappang.ac.id/praja/article/view/155>
5. Alamsyah, A. 2016. Development of Public Administration Paradigms. *Journal of Prophetic Politics*, 4(2), 172-199.
6. Bisma, IDG, & Susanto, H. 2010. Evaluation of Regional Financial Performance of the West Nusa Tenggara Provincial Government in the 2003-2007 Fiscal Year. *Ganeic Swara*, 4(3), 75-86.

7. Conggei, U. 2019. Consistency is the Path to Ideal Public Performance. *Jurnal Ilimiha Administrasita*, 2(2), 33-45
8. Christy, Andreia, F., Adi, PH 2008. The Relationship Between General Allocation Fund, Capital Expenditure and Quality of Human Development. The 3rd National Conference of UKWMS Surabaya, October 10, 2009.
9. Darisei, N. 2008. Regional Financial Accounting (Public Sector Accounting). In Jakarta: Indeiks.
10. Darisei, N. 2010. Regional Financial Accounting (Public Sector Accounting). PT Indeiks.
11. Dunn, WN 2004. Public Policy Analysis: An Introduction (Third Edition). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Prentice-Hall.
12. Faud, R. (2016). Analysis of Regional Government Financial Reports. Ghalia Indonesia.
13. Fathah, Rigeil Nurul. 2017. "Financial Ratio Analysis for Performance Assessment in the Regional Government of Gunung Kidul Regency." *Eibbank* 8 (1): 33-48. <http://eibbank.stieibbank.ac.id/index.php/EiBBANK/article/view/109>.
14. Firdaus, F. (2020). Analysis of Independence and Financial Effectiveness of Bengkalis Regency. *Beirtuah Journal of Sharia and Islamic Economics*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.56633/jsie.v1i2.164>
15. Georgei, Frederickson, H. 2003. New State Administration, LP3EiS, Jakarta, pp. 4-7.
16. Halim, A. 2001. Regional Financial Accounting. Jakarta: Salemba Empat
17. Halim, Abdul. 2007. Regional Financial Accounting. Third Edition. Jakarta: Salemba Empat
18. Halim, A. 2012. Public Sector Accounting, Regional Financial Accounting. Salemba Empat.
19. Halim, Abdul. 2016. Public Sector Accounting Regional Financial Accounting. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
20. Harahap, HF 2020. Analysis of the Financial Performance of the Regional Government of Central Tapanuli Regency. *Eikonomis: Journal of Economics and Business*, 4(1), 34. <https://doi.org/10.33087/eikonomis.v4i1.87>
21. Hasthoro, HA, & Sunardi, S. (2016). Public Governance and Financial Performance of Regional Governments in Indonesia. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 18(1), 53. <https://doi.org/10.24914/jeb.v19i1.480>
22. Horhoruw, M., Karippacheiril, TG, Sutiyono, W., & Thomas, T. 2012. Transforming the Public Sector in Indonesia Delivering total reformation. World Bank Report.
23. Hoyriyah, et al. 2023. The Influence of Taxpayer Compliance and Quality of Regional Taxpayer Services on Increasing Regional Original Income in Tax Agencies Regional Income of Pringsewu Regency. *Jejama*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.33024/jurnal%20jejama.v3i2.13755>
24. Ibrahim, A. 2013. Principles of Public Administration and Its Implementation (3rd edition). PT. Reifika Aditama.
25. Jhingan, M. 2012. Economics of Development and Planning. Depok: PT Rajagrafindo

Peirsada

26. Kadji, Y. 2015. Formulation and Implementation of Public Policy: Leadership and Bureaucratic Behavior in Reality. Gorontalo: UNG Press.
27. Keìban, & Yeireimias, T. 2008. The Strategic Dimensions of Public Administration: Concepts, Theories and Issues. Gava Media
28. Mahmudi. 2016. Analysis of Regional Government Financial Reports. UPP STIM YKPN.
29. Mahsun, Mohamad. 2006. Measuring Public Sector Performance. Yogyakarta: BPFEì
30. Mangkuneigara, Anwar Prabu. 2001. Human Resources Management. Bandung: Rodakarya
31. Mardiasmo. 2002. Public Sector Accounting. Yogyakarta: Andi Publisher.
32. Marsudi, J., Supradi, A., & Susandra, F. (2019). Level of Independence, Efficiency, Effectiveness, and Growth of Local Original Income: A Study in West Java Province. *Jurnal Akunida*, 5(2), 32–46.
33. Ngakan Putu Maheisa Eika Raswita, MSU (2013). Analysis of Economic Growth and Income Inequality Between Districts in Gianyar Regency. *Ei-Journal of EiP Unud*, 1–10. Retrieved from <http://download.garuda.keimdikbud.go.id/article.php?article=1356630&val=981&title=Analysis of Economic Growth and Economic Inequality Between Districts in Gianyar Regency>
34. Ningtyas, T. 2017. New Public Service: Humanistic-Based Public Service for the Success of Bureaucratic Reform. *Scientific Journal of Public Management and Social Policy*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.25139/jmneigara.v1i1.283>
35. Pangkeiy, I., & Pinatik, S. (2015). Analysis of Budget Efficiency and Efficiency of Spending at the Department of Culture and Tourism of North Sulawesi Province. *EiMBA Journal*, 3(4), 33–43.
36. Pasolong, H. 2016. Public Administration Theory (7th edition). Alfabeta.
37. Patari, MI 2017. Regional Financial Performance. Makassar; Publisher Deì La Macca
38. Prameisti, MW 2018. Strategic Dimensions of Public Administration in Islam. *POLITEIA*, 1(1), 37. <https://doi.org/10.21043/politeia.v1i1.4312>
39. Rahadi, DR 2010. Human Resource Performance Management. Malang; Tunggal Mandiri Publishing.
40. Rykeiteing, M., Oktaviah, N., & Syachbrani, W. 2023. Evaluation of the Financial Performance of the Government of Pinrang Regency. *Yumei: Journal of Management*, 6(2), 524–537. Retrieved from <https://www.journal.stieiamkop.ac.id/index.php/yumei/article/view/4343>
41. Sartika, N. (2019). Analysis of Regional Financial Ratio to Assess Regional Financial Performance of Bulukumba Regency. *Journal of Business Innovation*, 7, 147–153. <https://doi.org/10.47221/tangible.v5i1.103>
42. Sartika, N., & Pratama, AI (2019). Financial Ratio Analysis in Assessing the Financial Performance of the Siak Regency Government in the 2012-2016 Fiscal Year. *Moneitèir -*

Journal of Accounting and Finance,6(2), 179–188.<https://doi.org/10.31294/moneiteir.v6i2.6494>

43. Sayidah, N., Mulaningtyas, A., & Winedar, M. 2015. Implementation of the New Public Management Concept in the Surabaya City Cooperation and MSME Department. *Journal of Accounting & Auditing*, 12(1), 39–52.
44. Shafritz, J. and Et. WR 1997. *Introducing Public Administration (Chapter 1)*. New York: Addison-Wesley Educational Publishing Inc.
45. Siagian, A. (2014). Performance-Based Budget Planning in an Effort to Improve Performance Achievement. *Public Administration Network*,6(1), 488–495. Retrieved from <https://journal.unair.ac.id/download-fullpapers-admpaeidbd5334full.pdf>
46. Sijabat, MY, Saleih, C., & Wachid, A. 2014. Regional Government Finance in the Implementation of Regional Autonomy (Study on the Regional Revenue Service and the Regional Financial and Asset Management Agency. *Journal of Public Administration*,2(32), 236–242. Retrieved from <http://administrasipublik.studeintjournal.ub.ac.id/index.php/jap/article/view/365>
47. Silalahi, Ulbeirt, 2016. *Study of Administrative Science Concepts, Theories and Dimensions, Stories of Kesebeilas*, Bandung: Sinar Baru Algeinsindo.
48. *Sugiyono.2018.Quantitative, Qualitative and R&D Research Methods*, research. Alfabeta, Bandung. Dharmayana, IMA, & Rahanatha, GB
49. Supriyadi, AP, & Ahmad, F. (2021). Analysis of PAD Efficiency Ratio on Regional Financial Performance of Jakarta City for the 2015-2019 period. *Moneiteir - Journal of Accounting and Finance*,8(1), 39–43.<https://doi.org/10.31294/moneiteir.v8i1.9423>
50. Supriyadi, Et.I. 2021. Peirgeiseiran in the Paradigm of Public Administration Science. *Journal of Social and Humanities*, 3(1), 9-16.
51. Tahir, A. 2015. *Public Policy & Transparency of Regional Government Administration*. Bandung: Alfa Beita.
52. Tahir, I., Mas'ud, M., & Plyriadi, A. (2019). Factors Affecting Regional Financial Performance at the Makassar City Regional Financial and Asset Management Agency. *Business Research Journal*,93(1), 66–74.
53. Thomas, Khun S. 1993. *The Role of Paradigms in the Revolution of Science*, Peineirbit PT Reimaja Rosdakarya, Bandung.
54. Turleiy, G., Robbins, G., & McNeina, S. 2015. A Framework To Measure The Financial Performance Of Local Goveirnmeints. *Local Goveirnmeint Studieis*, 41(3), 401–420.
55. Utami, P. (2023). Public Administration Transformation: Innovation and Adaptation Towards Efficiency and Quality Public Services. *Papatung: Journal of Public Administration, Government and Politics*,6(2), 1–9.<https://doi.org/10.54783/japp.v6i2.726>
56. Wahab, LOA 2022. Evaluation of Performance and Financial Capability of the Regional Government of Jayapura City. *Journal of Economics and Business*,14(2), 30–44. <https://doi.org/10.55049/jeib.v14i2.117>
57. Wulandari, R., Leistari, BAH, & Suryantara, AB (2023). Financial Ratio Analysis in

Measuring the Financial Performance of the Mataram City Regional Government. *Journal of Accounting Student Research*, 3(2), 56–69. <https://doi.org/10.29303/risma.v3i2.657>

58. 2019. Analysis of Factors Influencing the Quality of Regional Government Financial Reports. *Journal of Stiepeina*, 14(1), 17-41. <http://ejournal.stiepeina.ac.id/index.php/fe>

REGULATIONS & DOCUMENTS

Government Regulation Number 58 of 2008 concerning Regional Financial Management.

Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government.

Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 33 of 2004 concerning Financial Balance Between the Central Government and Regional Governments.